

POLICY BRIEF

Resilient by Design: Policy Lessons from Ukraine's EdTech Emergency Response

Date March 2026

Authors Margi Bhatt
Kate Radford

DOI 10.53832/edtechhub.1223

About this document

Recommended citation

Bhatt, M., & Radford, K. (2026). *Resilient by Design: Policy Lessons from Ukraine's EdTech Emergency Response* [Policy Brief]. EdTech Hub. <https://doi.org/10.53832/edtechhub.1223>. Available at <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/3BDA5DH8>. Available under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Licence

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

This licence means you are free to share and adapt for any purpose, even commercially, as long as you give appropriate credit, provide a link to the licence, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use. Please refer to the link for more details.

Reviewers

Haani Mazari

About EdTech Hub

EdTech Hub is a global research partnership. Our goal is to empower people by giving them the evidence they need to make decisions about technology in education. Our [evidence library](#) is a repository of our latest research, findings, and wider literature on EdTech. As a global partnership, we seek to make our evidence available and accessible to those seeking EdTech solutions worldwide.

EdTech Hub is supported by UKAid, World Bank, and UNICEF. The views in this document do not necessarily reflect the views of these organisations.

To find out more about us, go to edtechhub.org/. Our evidence library can be found at docs.edtechhub.org/lib/.

Contents

<i>List of abbreviations and acronyms</i>	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Key findings	6
2.1. Pre-crisis digital transformation strategy: A foundation for resilience	6
A decade of reform	6
Digital governance infrastructure	6
A national digital learning platform for primary and secondary education	6
Data and assessment systems	7
2.2. When schools closed, learning continued	7
Multiple delivery models	7
Device access	8
Safe places to study	8
Exam continuity	8
Teacher professional development and support	9
2.3. Government stewardship of the humanitarian response	9
Donors and humanitarian partners aligned with national priorities	10
Private sector participation guided by government leadership	10
Adapting while learning	11
2.4. Remaining gaps: Equity, inclusion, and teacher well-being	11
Navigating multiple education delivery models	11
Children with disabilities	12
Digital divides	12
Teacher strain	13
Dual schooling abroad	13
3. Recommendations and conclusion	15
3.1. Recommendations	15
1. Invest early in digital transformation capacity	15
2. Keep education ministries at the centre	15
3. Simplify bureaucracy during crisis responses while preserving accountability	15
4. Leverage trust, align with humanitarian norms, and remain actively engaged	15
5. Prioritise inclusion from the outset	16
3.2. Conclusion	16
References	17

Abbreviations and acronyms

AUSO	All-Ukrainian School Online
Digital ID	Digital identification
ECW	Education Cannot Wait
EMIS	Education management information systems
GPE	Global Partnership for Education
IEA	Institute of Educational Analytics (Ukraine)
IIEP	(UNESCO) International Institute for Educational Planning
INEE	Inter-agency Network for Education in Emergencies
MHPSS	Mental Health and Psychosocial Support
MoES	Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
SSEQU	State Service of Education Quality of Ukraine
UCEQA	Ukrainian Center for Educational Quality Assessment
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

1. Introduction

Since the full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, as many as 6.4 million school-aged children have experienced disruption to schooling, with over 1.2 million Ukrainian students lacking safe access to in-person education due to widespread school closures as of mid-2025 ([↑GPE, 2025b](#); [↑UNESCO, 2025b](#)). As physical classrooms became unsafe or inaccessible post-invasion, the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (MoES) leveraged pre-existing investments in digital infrastructure to pivot rapidly to remote and hybrid learning ([↑EdCamp Ukraine, 2021](#); [↑Donnelly et al., 2021](#)). Ukraine's government-led digital transformation has acted as a critical tool for resilience. The Ministry's emergency education response demonstrates strong central leadership by coordinating international donors, the private sector, and humanitarian agencies around a unified national goal ([↑GPE, 2024](#)).

This policy brief draws on the qualitative research study,¹ *Resilient by Design: Ukraine's EdTech Emergency Response* ([↑Bhatt & Radford, 2025](#)) and offers specific insights for governments and their United Nations (UN), non-governmental organisation (NGO), and private-sector partners on using EdTech to maintain learning continuity during conflict and crises. The brief particularly highlights the role of strong government leadership, the value of pre-crisis technology investment, and the benefits of effective engagement with humanitarian systems actors and coordination mechanisms.

¹ The qualitative research study, conducted between April and September 2025, is informed by a review of 107 documents and 18 interviews with government, humanitarian, donor, NGO, academic, and private-sector stakeholders.

2. Key findings

This section synthesises the core lessons from Ukraine's education response, examining how pre-existing digital infrastructure, multiple delivery models, and strong government stewardship enabled continuity of learning. It also presents the critical gaps that persist for vulnerable learners and the teaching workforce.

2.1. Pre-crisis digital transformation strategy: A foundation for resilience

Ukraine's ability to pivot quickly to distance and hybrid learning was rooted in decisions and investments in digital infrastructure made long before the 2022 invasion ([MoES Ukraine, 2023b](#)). Below are important policy initiatives which have contributed to the Ukrainian education system's resilience after the 2022 invasion.

A decade of reform

Beginning in 2016, Ukraine implemented major reforms under the New Ukrainian School (NUS) initiative ([MoES Ukraine, 2016](#)). These reforms modernised the curriculum, strengthened teacher professional development, and expanded inclusion. Importantly, they prioritised digital readiness across the system ([Nazarenko, 2025](#)).

Digital governance infrastructure

In 2019, the government established the Ministry of Digital Transformation (MoDT) and launched Diia, a national digital public services platform used for identity verification, registration, and e-documents ([Mamatova & Sydorenko, 2020](#)). Diia quickly became a backbone for public administration ([Vyhovska et al., 2025](#)). Its authentication and e-signature tools later enabled secure access to examinations and learning platforms, as well as financial support for displaced families ([Kyiv Global Government Technology Centre, 2025](#); [Ukrainian National News, 2024](#)).

A national digital learning platform for primary and secondary education

During the Covid-19 pandemic, the MoES and the national NGO Osvitoria launched All-Ukrainian School Online (AUSO), a nationwide platform offering curriculum-aligned lessons for Grades 5-11 ([AUSO, 2022](#); [hundrED, 2025](#); [MoES Ukraine, 2020](#)). To reach households without reliable internet, these lessons aired on television channels ([Euro Health Observatory, 2020](#);

↑[MoES Ukraine, 2020](#)). Teacher organisations such as EdCamp ran nationwide online training ‘marathons’, building practical digital pedagogy skills among tens of thousands of teachers (↑[EdCamp Ukraine, 2021](#)).

Data and assessment systems

Ukraine also invested in modern education management information systems (EMIS) and computer-based national examinations (↑[IEA, 2022](#); ↑[Interoperable Europe, 2024](#)). The Ukrainian Center for Educational Quality Assessment had already begun transitioning to online test delivery before the war; this preparation proved valuable when students later needed to sit exams from shelters or abroad (↑[SSEQU, 2023](#); ↑[Interoperable Europe, 2024](#)).

Key insight

Digital transformation is not only a modernisation goal but also an essential mechanism for resilience. When governments make pre-crisis investments in digital infrastructure, they are better positioned to absorb shocks and maintain service delivery during emergencies.

2.2. When schools closed, learning continued

When schools could not open safely, the MoES mobilised a broad set of measures to maintain learning, combining alternative delivery models, targeted device provision, community learning spaces, adapted examination systems, and rapid support for teachers. This range of measures, in various combinations, helped sustain learning through prolonged disruption and is outlined below.

Multiple delivery models

Ukraine maintained teaching and learning through multiple delivery models (↑[UNESCO, 2023a](#)). The national online platforms, such as AUSO, were later complemented by Diia. The Osvita and Mriia platforms were used alongside school-run virtual classes, televised lessons in the early days of the invasion, and low-connectivity options, including offline digital resources, radio, and printed self-learning packs (↑[Eurydice, 2025](#); ↑[Government of Ukraine, 2025](#); ↑[UNICEF, 2024c](#)). The layered mix of online, broadcast, offline, and in-person options allowed schools to adjust delivery as safety, electricity, and connectivity conditions changed.

Device access

As millions of children lost access to safe classrooms, the lack of access to laptops and tablets became a barrier to online learning. In early 2024, the

MoES launched the [Device Coalition](#),² which brought together private companies, UN agencies, donors, and NGOs under a single national distribution plan ([↑UNESCO, 2025c](#)). Between 2022 and 2025, approximately 172,000 devices were delivered to children and 100,700 to teachers, with support from approximately 30 coalition partners ([↑EU4Digital, 2024](#); [↑Global Business Coalition for Education, 2022](#); [↑UNESCO, 2023a](#)). MoES published [dashboards](#)³ that tracked the number of devices each school received and the remaining gaps, reinforcing transparency and aligning with national continuity plans ([↑MoES Ukraine & ECW, 2024](#)).

Safe places to study

For children unable to learn at home, due to power outages, poor connectivity, crowded shelters, or unstable housing, NGOs and UN agencies opened Digital Learning Centres (DLCs) ([↑MoES Ukraine, 2024](#); [↑UNICEF, 2025b](#)). These hubs offered electricity, Wi-Fi, psychosocial support activities, and staff who could help children complete assignments or access online lessons on AUSO ([↑Education Cluster et al., 2023](#); [↑UNICEF, 2024a](#)).

Beginning in mid-2022 and reinforced in 2023, the MoES issued directives stating that schools could reopen for in-person learning only if they had an operational, certified shelter on site or immediate access to one nearby ([↑Savisko & Karakai, 2025](#)). This requirement became the defining criterion for determining whether teaching and learning could take place face-to-face or needed to shift to remote or hybrid modes. It also made community-level solutions even more important and complemented national digital learning platforms.

Exam continuity

Ukraine also maintained pathways to higher education. The national multi-subject test (NMT), taken by Grade 11 students seeking admission to higher education, shifted to secure computer-based delivery both within Ukraine and in host countries ([↑Ukrainian National News, 2024](#)). Students used digital IDs via Diia to register and authenticate, enabling them to continue their studies despite displacement ([↑UCEQA, 2024](#)).

² See <https://www.dcoalition.org.ua/en>. Retrieved 19 March 2026.

³ See <https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/d156064e-81a3-4df1-b0ca-ed8132731e5f/page/kxPID>. Retrieved 19 March 2026.

Teacher professional development and support

MoES and partners expanded short-format online professional development opportunities to support teachers, including access to helpdesks, peer learning and support groups, and resource libraries to give teachers practical guidance on using national platforms, using EdTech as a pedagogical tool, and adapting curricula for hybrid and interrupted schedules (↑[MoES Ukraine, 2023a](#); ↑[UNESCO, 2024a](#); ↑[UNESCO, 2024b](#)). Humanitarian actors added training on Mental Health and Psychosocial Support (MHPSS), recognising teachers' central role in supporting learners coping with stress and displacement (↑[GPE, 2025a](#); ↑[UNICEF, 2024b](#)). This combination of support, focused on technical issues and well-being, helped teachers stay connected with students and support their learning despite ongoing disruptions.

Key insight

Ukraine's experience shows that learning continuity in unstable emergency settings relies on a mix of delivery models—from face-to-face instruction when safe, to hybrid and blended arrangements during periods of instability, to fully remote and offline options when schools are closed. Devices, connectivity, safe study spaces, television broadcasting, printed materials, flexible exam systems, and targeted support for teachers all work together to keep children learning; no single platform or model is sufficient on its own. Learning continues because the system offers multiple, overlapping routes that children and teachers can use depending on their circumstances.

2.3. Government stewardship of the humanitarian response

Education response in crisis contexts can become fragmented when many actors enter the scene (↑[IIEP-UNESCO, 2022](#); ↑[INEE, 2024](#)). The MoES in Ukraine asserted and maintained strong leadership from the outset, anchoring partners in national platforms and procedures rather than allowing a patchwork of separate projects. Partners noted that when compared to other emergency responses, Ukraine's ministry “*wasn't just responsive—it was a directive*” (key informant interview in ↑[Bhatt & Radford \(2025, p. 34\)](#)).

MoES's long-term Strategic Action Plan (to 2027) continued to guide decisions amid the full-scale invasion, framing emergency measures as part of a longer-term reform and recovery trajectory (↑[MoES Ukraine,](#)

2023b). Important examples of MoES's stewardship of the humanitarian education response are highlighted below.

Donors and humanitarian partners aligned with national priorities

The Education Cluster, led by UNICEF and Save the Children, worked “*in partnership with the government*” rather than in parallel (↑[Bhatt & Radford, 2025](#), p. 36). The MoES was treated as a primary actor, with government representatives attending regular cluster meetings and participating in data sharing.

Education Cannot Wait, the Global Partnership for Education, UNICEF, UNESCO, and others channelled funds into MoES-defined priorities towards its Digital Transformation Strategy, such as digital access, teacher professional development (including MHPSS), and data systems (↑[GPE, 2023](#); ↑[MoES Ukraine & ECW, 2024](#); ↑[UNESCO, 2023b](#)). Across funding mechanisms, pooled, flexible, government-aligned financing supported both emergency digital delivery and structural investment, such as EMIS strengthening, standardised teacher training, and inclusion education policies (e.g., accessibility requirements), under a single national framework.

Private sector participation guided by government leadership

Major tech companies, including Google, Microsoft, and HP, engaged through government-led coalitions such as the Global Education Coalition and the Device Coalition (↑[Smith, 2022](#); ↑[UNESCO, 2022](#); ↑[UNESCO, 2025c](#)). They contributed devices, cloud support, cybersecurity services, and platform upgrades within a framework defined by the MoES, ensuring compatibility with Ukrainian national policy standards and requirements, including those related to curriculum, equity, and infrastructure. UNESCO acted as a broker, but MoES set standards for platforms, device allocation, and data integration, ensuring private support served public objectives and that donated goods were logged in official registries (↑[MoES Ukraine & ECW, 2024](#); ↑[UNESCO, 2023b](#)).

Adapting while learning

MoES was initially unfamiliar with humanitarian planning cycles and cluster procedures but adapted quickly through engagement, prompting donors to streamline approvals, adjust procurement rules, and align timelines with national plans (↑[Bhatt & Radford, 2025](#)). Interviews and cluster reports describe an iterative learning process in which the ministry

adjusted communication channels and clarified mandates([↑Bhatt & Radford, 2025](#)).

Cluster updates note routine bilingual coordination (Ukrainian/English) and dual-language guidance, which reduced friction for international partners while keeping national actors central to decision-making ([↑Education Cluster & Save the Children, 2025](#); [↑Ukraine Shelter Cluster, 2025](#); [↑UNHCR, 2024](#)).

Key insights

By remaining the primary steward of the education system and requiring partners to support the national plan rather than operate independently, Ukraine prevented fragmentation of the emergency education response. They ensured that international support strengthened national ownership and aligned with national education system strategies.

Ukraine's ability to navigate both domestic policy and to engage directly with international humanitarian norms enabled flexible funding, steering international resources towards its own national priorities.

2.4. Remaining gaps: Equity, inclusion, and teacher well-being

Despite its successes, Ukraine's response exposed limitations common to digitally mediated education in crisis. Several key limitations are outlined below.

Navigating multiple education delivery models

While multiple education delivery models, combining in-person, remote, and hybrid options, are essential for access, emerging data highlights the challenges posed by complex learning arrangements. In May 2024, the MoES and the Ukrainian Center for Educational Quality Assessment (UCEQA) conducted a nationwide monitoring study involving more than 4,400 Grade 8 students to assess learning outcomes in Ukrainian. The results revealed that education delivery models significantly influence performance ([↑MoES Ukraine & UCEQA, 2024](#)). Students in fully remote and fully in-person learning models showed comparable learning outcomes, whereas students in hybrid models, alternating between online and offline instruction, performed marginally worse. Additionally, the type of digital device used proved critical; students using laptops or desktops consistently outperformed those using smartphones. The study also noted broader disparities: girls slightly outperformed boys, and there were significant

regional variations, with students in Kyiv and southern *oblasts* (administrative regions) achieving the highest average scores. This assessment did not disaggregate results by disability status. Further evaluation is required to understand how different delivery models performed across the humanitarian education response more broadly, for example, with primary grade students.

Children with disabilities

Before the full-scale invasion, approximately 7,000 learners were in special classrooms and over 40,000 in inclusive classrooms, with nearly 11,000 receiving home-based instruction under pedagogical supervision, indicating a substantial baseline need for specialised support ([↑MoES Ukraine & ECW, 2024](#)). A national needs assessment later found that nearly 40% of communities lacked the technical means to organise learning for children with special educational needs, and 60% reported urgent needs for equipment and specialised teacher training ([↑MoES Ukraine & ECW, 2024](#)). As learning moved online, children with disabilities were more likely to lack assistive technologies, individualised support, or consistent access to teaching assistants. They were at higher risk of being left out of virtual classes ([↑MoES Ukraine & ECW, 2024](#)).

Digital divides

Rural communities, frontline oblasts, and low-income households face persistent device and connectivity gaps ([↑Brown, 2024](#); [↑European Training Foundation, 2021](#)). Even with large-scale device distributions, humanitarian situation reports and distribution-tracking platforms note that demand continues to outstrip supply and that electricity and connectivity remain unreliable in many areas ([↑Brown, 2024](#); [↑Emergency Telecommunications Cluster, 2025](#)).

Teacher strain

Teachers carry a heavy load. Early emergency snapshots in Ukraine reported that around 90% of teachers experienced worsening psychological well-being, alongside widespread signs of child distress ([↑Global Education Cluster, 2023](#)). Despite measures to support teachers with technical professional development opportunities and MHPSS training, frontline accounts describe teachers delivering lessons from shelters, coping with power cuts, managing mixed-ability hybrid classes, and caring for their own displaced families ([↑Plan International, 2025](#); [↑UNICEF, 2025a](#)).

Dual schooling abroad

Many displaced Ukrainian children are enrolled in schools across Europe. Particularly in the first years after the 2022 invasion, many attempted to follow both the Ukrainian curriculum online and host-country programmes, a demanding arrangement that led to fatigue and sporadic disengagement ([↑UNESCO, 2025a](#); [↑UNHCR, 2025](#)). Language barriers and inconsistent recognition of Ukrainian credits compounded these challenges ([↑UNHCR, 2025](#)).

Recognition of learning acquired abroad has since been regulated through MoES procedures, but implementation remains complex at the school level and continues to require guidance and support ([↑MoES Ukraine, 2025](#)).

Key insight

Ukraine's experience offers transferable lessons for any system planning to ensure educational continuity under crisis conditions.

Evaluation findings in Ukraine suggest that simpler delivery models may outperform complex ones, hybrid arrangements produced marginally weaker outcomes than either fully remote or fully in-person instruction, suggesting that logistical complexity can itself become a barrier to learning. Device quality matters as much as device access. Students using laptops or desktops consistently outperformed smartphone users, underscoring the importance of understanding each device type's limits and capabilities to support specific learning needs.

Children with disabilities require proactive planning. Gaps in assistive technology, specialist training, and technical capacity are predictable and should be addressed in preparedness frameworks before disruption occurs.

Teacher well-being is an operational concern, not a peripheral one. With around 90% of Ukrainian teachers reporting worsening psychological

well-being, mental health support must be treated as a core component of system continuity.

For displaced learners, dual curriculum arrangements carry a real risk of fatigue. Early coordination on credit recognition and language support between national and host-country authorities can significantly reduce this burden.

3. Recommendations and conclusion

Drawing on the successes and challenges of the Ukraine case study, this section outlines recommendations for policymakers to build resilient education systems before crises emerge. It concludes with a summary of how government leadership and early digital investment can transform emergency response.

3.1. Recommendations

These recommendations are intended for governments and international partners preparing for or responding to educational crises.

1. Invest early in digital transformation capacity

Digital identity systems, learning platforms, and computer-based assessments all proved critical when Ukraine's schools closed overnight. Governments that invest in these foundations as preparedness spending will be better positioned to pivot during crises.

2. Keep education ministries at the centre

Ukraine prevented fragmentation by requiring partners to align with national platforms and priorities rather than operate independently. Ministries should establish clear coordination protocols with humanitarian actors from the outset, including regular joint planning and data sharing, so that international support strengthens rather than displaces national systems.

3. Simplify bureaucracy during crisis responses while preserving accountability

Ukraine's MoES used public dashboards to track device distribution and maintain transparency under pressure. Fast-track procurement and adaptive funding are essential in crises, but should be anchored in visible reporting tools that maintain humanitarian accountability norms.

4. Leverage trust, align with humanitarian norms, and remain actively engaged

Ukraine's MoES learnt about humanitarian planning cycles and humanitarian education cluster procedures through direct, iterative engagement. Governments should invest in building this institutional literacy before crises emerge, so that when international

funding flows, ministries can support national education system priorities, while ensuring adequate support for affected populations.

5. Prioritise inclusion from the outset

Nearly 40% of Ukrainian communities lacked the means to support children with special educational needs online. Device distribution strategies, platform design, and teacher training should all include explicit inclusion requirements, not as add-ons, but as baseline standards built into procurement and partnership agreements.

3.2. Conclusion

Ukraine's experience shows that resilience in education is built long before a crisis occurs. Years of reform, investment in digital public infrastructure, and teacher development laid the foundation for an emergency response that protected learning at a national scale. Strong government leadership then ensured that both international and domestic partners reinforced rather than replaced national systems.

For other contexts, the central message is: build resilience now. Digital systems, inclusive design, and coordinated governance are not emergency tools. They are rooted in core public infrastructure. When a crisis arises, they determine whether children continue learning.

References

This bibliography is available digitally in our evidence library at <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/3BDA5DH8>

- AUSO. (2022). *A Guide to the All-Ukrainian Online School*. <https://uied.org.ua/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/vseukrayinska-shkola-onlajn-angl.pdf>. (details)
- Bhatt, M., & Radford, K. (2025). *Resilient by Design: Ukraine's EdTech Emergency Response. A qualitative study [Country Summary and Case Study]*. EdTech Hub. <https://doi.org/10.53832/edtechhub.1122>. Available from <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/P6UGNRFA>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. (details)
- Brown, S. (2024, February 22). Educating Ukraine's children is critical to its future. *Financial Times*. <https://www.ft.com/content/7af8a288-2762-4846-a021-8ba161e003cd>. (details)
- Donnelly, R., Patrinos, H. A., & James Gresham. (2021). *The Impact of COVID-19 on Education – Recommendations and Opportunities for Ukraine*. World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/opinion/2021/04/02/the-impact-of-covid-19-on-education-recommendations-and-opportunities-for-ukraine>. (details)
- EU4Digital. (2024, May 10). *Education in times of war: Device Coalition and UNICEF provide schoolchildren with 39,000 laptops*. <https://eufordigital.eu/education-in-times-of-war-device-coalition-and-unicef-provide-schoolchildren-with-39000-laptops/>. (details)
- EdCamp Ukraine. (2021). *EdCamp Days Report: EdCamp Ukraine's Activities 2018–2020*. EdCamp Ukraine. <https://www.edcamp.ua/en/public-reports/>. (details)
- Education Cluster, & Save the Children. (2025). *Ukraine Education Cluster Strategy 2025*. <https://reliefweb.int/report/ukraine/ukraine-education-cluster-strategy-2025-enuk>. (details)
- Education Cluster, Save the Children, & UNICEF. (2023). *Ukraine Education Cluster: Basic standards for Digital Learning Centers*. <https://reliefweb.int/report/ukraine/ukraine-education-cluster-basic-standards-digital-learning-centers-enuk>. (details)

- Emergency Telecommunications Cluster. (2025). *Ukraine Conflict: ETC Situation Report #48*.
<https://www.etcluster.org/sites/default/files/documents/ETC%20Ukraine%20SitRep%20-%202025-06-30-%2348.pdf?> (details)
- Euro Health Observatory. (2020). *Ukraine Policy Responses [COVID-19 Health System Response Monitor (HSRM)]*.
<https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/monitors/hsrcm/hsrcm-countries/hsrcm/ukraine>. (details)
- European Training Foundation. (2021). *Ukraine Education, Training and Employment Developments 2021*.
https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/CFI_Ukraine_2021.pdf? (details)
- Eurydice. (2025). *Ukraine: Digital transformation of education as a strategic path to resilience and innovation*.
<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/news/ukraine-digital-transformation-education-strategic-path-resilience-and-innovation>. (details)
- Global Business Coalition for Education. (2022, November 28). *Laptops give Ukrainian children a lifeline to education*.
<https://gbc-education.org/insights/laptops-give-ukrainian-children-a-lifeline-to-education/>. (details)
- Global Education Cluster. (2023). *2022 Achievements: Ukraine*.
<https://www.educationcluster.net/2022-achievements-ukraine>. (details)
- Global Partnership for Education (GPE). (2023, April 25). *Approval of Multiplier Grant to Ukraine as Accelerated Funding*. Available from <https://www.globalpartnership.org/node/document/download?file=document%2Ffile%2F2023-04-gpe-board-decision-multiplier-grant-ukraine.pdf>. (details)
- Global Partnership for Education (GPE). (2024). *Guidelines: System Capacity Grant*. Available from <https://www.globalpartnership.org/node/document/download?file=document%2Ffile%2F2024-07-gpe-guidelines-system-capacity-grant.pdf>. (details)
- Global Partnership for Education (GPE). (2025a). *Ukraine: Education brings mental health support to children*.
<https://www.globalpartnership.org/results/country-journeys/ukraine-education-brings-mental-health-support-children>. (details)

- Global Partnership for Education (GPE). (2025b, January). *Ukraine: Making education accessible when schools are closed*.
[https://www.globalpartnership.org/results/country-journeys/ukraine-making-education-accessible-when-schools-are-closed#:~:text=Thanks%20to%20a%20combination%20of,places%20where%20schools%20cannot%20reopen](https://www.globalpartnership.org/results/country-journeys/ukraine-making-education-accessible-when-schools-are-closed#:~:text=Thanks%20to%20a%20combination%20of,places%20where%20schools%20cannot%20reopen.). (details)
- Government of Ukraine. (2025, April 9). *Mriya: Ukraine's innovative educational ecosystem*.
<https://digitalstate.gov.ua/news/govtech/mriia-innovatsiyna-osvitnia-ekosystema-ukrayiny>. (details)
- hundrED. (2025, April 30). *The All-Ukrainian Online School*.
<https://hundred.org/en/innovations/the-all-ukrainian-online-school?>. (details)
- IIEP-UNESCO, & UNICEF. (2022). *Strengthening Ministry of Education Engagement and Leadership in Rapid Education in Emergency Response* [Policy Brief].
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000383722>. (details)
- Institute of Educational Analytics. (2022). *The Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine approved the regulations on the software and hardware complex "Automated Information Complex of Educational Management" (AICEM)*.
<https://iea.gov.ua/en/the-cabinet-of-ministers-of-ukraine-approved-the-regulations-on-the-software-and-hardware-complex-automated-information-complex-of-educational-management-aicom/>. (details)
- Inter-agency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE). (2024). *Minimum Standards for Education: Preparedness, Response, Recovery*. <https://inee.org/minimum-standards>. (details)
- Interoperable Europe. (2024, July 11). *Ukraine: 2024 Digital Public Administration Factsheet*.
https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/inline-files/NIFO_2024%20Supporting%20Document_Ukraine_vFinal_rev.pdf. (details)
- Kyiv Global Government Technology Centre. (2025). *Diia Ecosystem*.
<https://www.kyivgovtechcentre.org/diia-ecosystem>. (details)
- Mamatova, T., & Sydorenko, N. (2020). The system of administrative services in Ukraine: Features of legal regulation. *Public Administration Aspects*, 8(6), 164–177. <https://doi.org/10.15421/1520115>. Available from <https://aspects.org.ua/index.php/journal/article/view/835>. (details)

- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. (2016). *The New Ukrainian School: Conceptual Principles*.
<https://mon.gov.ua/static-objects/mon/sites/1/zagalna%20serednya/Book-ENG.pdf>. (details)
- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. (2020). *Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine—April 6, All-Ukrainian Online School launched on YouTube channel of Ministry of Education and Science and 14 TV channels and media resources*.
<https://www.kmu.gov.ua/en/news/6-kvitnya-na-youtube-kanali-mon-ta-shche-na-14-telekanalah-ta-mediaresursah-startuvala-vseukrayinska-shkola-onlajn>. (details)
- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. (2023a, September 25). *Coursera extends free access to courses for Ukrainian higher education institutions*.
<https://mon.gov.ua/en/news/coursera-extends-free-access-to-courses-for-ukrainian-higher-education-institutions?> (details)
- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. (2023b). *Strategic Action Plan by 2027*. Government of Ukraine.
<https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/en/2023/strategic-action-plan-ministry-education-and-science-ukraine-2027>. (details)
- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. (2024). *Education Digest (Pilot issue)*.
<https://mon.gov.ua/static-objects/mon/sites/1/mizhnarodna/2024/12/30/education-digest-moes-december-2024-30-12.pdf>. (details)
- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. (2025). *Ukraine: Recognition of schoolchildren’s learning outcomes acquired abroad is now regulated*.
<https://eurydice.iea.gov.ua/news/ukraine-recognition-of-schoolchildrens-learning-outcomes-acquired-abroad-is-now-regulated>. (details)
- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, & Education Cannot Wait. (2024). *Multi-Year Resilience Programme (MYRP) Ukraine 2024-2026*.
https://www.educationcannotwait.org/sites/default/files/2024-03/ecw_myrp_for_ukraine_2024-2026.pdf. (details)
- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, & Ukrainian Center for Educational Quality Assessment. (2024). *Nationwide Monitoring Study of the Quality of Education in the Institutions of General Secondary Education Under Martial Law*.
https://sqe.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/ZVIT_Test_uchni_6i8kl_SQE-may2024_pres09.10.2024web.pdf. (details)

Nazarenko, Y. (2025). *Ukraine's Education Policy as a Pillar for Successful Rebuilding* [Policy Brief]. Foundation for European Progressive Studies.

<https://feps-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Ukraines-education-policy-as-a-pillar-for-successful-rebuilding.pdf?> (details)

Plan International. (2025). Three years of war in Ukraine: Education disruptions deepen mental health crisis for children. *Plan International EU Liaison Office*.

<https://plan-international.org/eu/news/2025/02/24/three-years-ukraine-war/>. (details)

Savisko, M., & Karakai, A. (2025). *Lost Lessons Due to Air Raid Alerts: How Many—and What Can Be Done?* Vox Ukraine.

<https://voxukraine.org/en/lost-lessons-due-to-air-raid-alerts-how-many-and-what-can-be-done>. (details)

Smith, B. (2022, November 3). Extending our vital technology support for Ukraine. *Microsoft On the Issues*.

<https://blogs.microsoft.com/on-the-issues/2022/11/03/our-tech-support-ukraine/>. (details)

The State Service of Education Quality of Ukraine. (2023, February 21). *The State Service of Education Quality of Ukraine presented EvaluEd system*.

<https://sqe.gov.ua/en/state-service-of-education-quality-of-ukraine-presented-evalued-system/>. (details)

UNESCO. (2022). *Ukraine: 50,000 computers provided to teachers by Google and UNESCO*.

<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/ukraine-50000-computers-provided-teachers-google-and-unesco>. (details)

UNESCO. (2023a). *Education in Ukraine: UNESCO mobilizes US\$12 million to step up its action on the ground*.

<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/education-ukraine-unesco-mobilizes-us12-million-step-its-action-ground>. (details)

UNESCO. (2023b). *Strengthening resilience of education system in Ukraine for emergency response and recovery*. Available from

<https://www.globalpartnership.org/node/document/download?file=document%2Ffile%2F2024-02-program-document-ukraine-unesco.pdf>. (details)

UNESCO. (2023c). *Ukraine: UNESCO mobilizes support for learning continuity*.

<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/ukraine-unesco-mobilizes-support-learning-continuity>. (details)

UNESCO. (2024a). *More than 48,000 Ukrainian teachers enrolled in UNESCO's "Digital teacher" training*.

<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/more-48000-ukrainian-teachers-enrolled-unescos-digital-teacher-training>. (details)

UNESCO. (2024b). *Ukraine: UNESCO trains 50,000 teachers on digital pedagogy*.

<https://ukraine.un.org/en/249121-ukraine-unesco-trains-50000-teachers-digital-pedagogy>. (details)

UNESCO. (2025a). *Education for Ukrainian refugee learners in European host countries*. <https://www.unesco.org/en/ukraine-war/education>. (details)

UNESCO. (2025b, June 26). *How UNESCO's Global Education Coalition supports learning continuity in Ukraine*.

<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/how-unescos-global-education-coalition-supports-learning-continuity-ukraine>. (details)

UNESCO. (2025c). *Public-private partnerships to bridge gaps in education continuity in times of crises: The Ukraine case study*.

<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/public-private-partnerships-bridge-gaps-education-continuity-times-crises-ukraine-case-study>. (details)

UNHCR. (2024). *Ukraine: Protection Cluster National meeting minutes: 14 August 2024*.

<https://reliefweb.int/report/ukraine/ukraine-protection-cluster-national-meeting-minutes-14-august-2024-enuk>. (details)

UNHCR. (2025). *New data insights reveal both progress and challenges for Ukrainian refugee students' education in Europe*. UNHCR Europe.

<https://www.unhcr.org/europe/news/announcements/new-data-insights-reveal-both-progress-and-challenges-ukrainian-refugee-students>. (details)

UNICEF. (2024a). *Ukraine Humanitarian Situation Report No. 42*.

<https://www.unicef.org/media/161591/file/Ukraine-Humanitarian-Situation-Report-No.-42%2C-31-July-2024.pdf>. (details)

UNICEF. (2024b). *Ukraine Humanitarian Situation Report No. 46*.

<https://www.unicef.org/ukraine/en/media/49676/file/UNICEF%20Ukraine>

[e%20Humanitarian%20Situation%20Report%20No.46%201-30%20November%202024.pdf.pdf](#). (details)

UNICEF. (2024c). *UNICEF distributes learning kits for distance learning in Ukraine*.

<https://www.unicef.org/ukraine/en/stories/unicef-distributes-learning-kits-for-distance-learning>. (details)

UNICEF. (2025a). *4.6 million children in Ukraine face ongoing educational barriers as fourth academic year during war begins*.

<https://www.unicef.org/ukraine/en/press-releases/back-to-school>. (details)

UNICEF. (2025b). *Ukraine Humanitarian Situation Report No. 49*.

https://www.unicef.org/ukraine/en/media/52401/file/UNICEF%20Ukraine%20Humanitarian%20Situation%20Report_49_FINAL.pdf.pdf. (details)

Ukraine Shelter Cluster. (2025). *Minutes of NSC Meeting 30.04.25*.

<https://s3.eu-north-1.amazonaws.com/cdn.sheltercluster.org/public/docs/Minutes%20of%20NSC%20Meeting%2030.04.25.pdf?>. (details)

Ukrainian Center for Educational Quality Assessment. (2024). *Testing 2024 abroad*. <https://testportal.gov.ua/en/nmt-2024-abroad/?>. (details)

Ukrainian National News. (2024, March 25). *Applicants can register for NMT through Diia: How to do it*. Ukrainian National News (UNN).

<https://unn.ua/en/news/applicants-can-register-for-nmt-through-diia-how-to-do-it>. (details)

Vyhovska, V., Sholudko, V., & Balytska, M. (2025). *State Digital Transformation in Ukraine: 2019–2024 Review*. Vox Ukraine.

<https://voxukraine.org/en/state-digital-transformation-in-ukraine-2019-2024-review>. (details)